
Analysis of English language systems using technology

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Abstract:

The current century is known for using technology in every perspective of life. In English language teaching systems, technology has become an unavoidable tool as it provides resources online. The research is going to analysis of English language systems using technology. English language learning with modern technology made up of multimedia devices, mobile phones, audio and video sources from multimedia, and even sources from social media have been unique tools of language learning classrooms. Technology-based language classrooms create more exposure to the second language than traditional teaching methods. The educator should be encouraged to use immense resources by using technology. The experience of the students who learn in the technology-based language classroom does not end with the classroom fences; it provides the experience of the real world. As an academicians, the researcher imposes the use of technology in the language-teaching classroom. Education planners can make a technology plan that is mindfully coordinated with the designed curriculum.

Keywords: technology, traditional methods, practical classes.

The current century is known for using technology in every perspective of life. Education is one such aspect where technology has played an important role in recent years. During this 21st century, it is possible to share knowledge from all over the world with the help of technology. Learning a second language is an important element that provides opportunities for international communication. The research is going to analysis of English language systems using technology.

In English language teaching systems, technology has become an unavoidable tool as it provides resources online. English language learning with modern technology made up of multimedia devices, mobile phones, audio and video sources from multimedia, and even sources from social media have been unique tools of language learning classrooms. In the process of practicing pronunciation and lexicalization, the learners can use videos and the internet to become familiar with the speaking of native speakers.

Technology has always been a significant part of the teaching profession, for it helps the teachers to encourage and assist the learning process of the students easily. The traditional classroom is not enough for the language learning process.

Issues with the traditional method of teaching:

The outdated methods of teaching the English language in the classroom depend on prescribed textbooks and blackboards. The teachers have to completely depend upon the accurate curriculum given to them.

The result of the student's learning process is formed based on reproducing the information received in the classroom. The importance is not given to the understanding of the text.

Traditional methods of teaching language may lead to boredom as it relies on the set of curriculum but not on the effective learning outcomes.

It is not possible for the learners to listen and practice the native speakers' pronunciation in the English language classroom until or unless the teacher is a native speaker.

Technology-based language classrooms create more exposure to the second language than traditional teaching methods. The educator should be encouraged to use immense resources by using technology. The resources include videos, images, eBooks, articles from online, and audio files that can be taken as teaching materials. These resources are flexible and upgraded, and they can be used as powerful tools for language teaching in the classroom. The experience of the students who learn from the technology-based language classroom does not end with the classroom fences; and it provides the experience of the real world. It pays way for practical classes in spite of theory-based classes. From the teacher's

point of view, it helps them to develop their skills based on technology and new teaching methodologies.

Alqahtani Mofare, in an article entitled "The Use of Technology in English Language Teaching," proves:

According to statistics conducted on random samples of students...the analysis of students' performance showed that 75% to 95% achieve high results in their attainment in English, unlike those who are taught by traditional means, their achievement rates are very low. In addition, the study revealed that interaction with teachers and the overall response of students in the classroom had improved significantly when using modern techniques in teaching English, as the interaction with teachers using modern media reached more than 90%, unlike those who are taught by traditional means have less than 50% interaction with teachers. Thus, it is clear that studies and surveys have shown that students are more inclined to learn from E-curriculum (173-174)

Use of software solutions in language learning:

The beginning of the language learning process is to learn how to pronounce in the second language. Listening to the videos on the pronunciation of native speakers would help the students to observe the pronunciation and reproduce it as near as a native speaker. Students can also record their own pronunciation and compare it to the pronunciation of native speakers.

From the above discussion, it is clear that technology is an unpreventable

tool in the language classroom. As an academician, the researcher imposes the use of technology in the language-teaching classroom. Education planners can make a technology plan that is mindfully coordinated with the designed curriculum. The educators should analyze what sort of approach would be effective while implementing the technology in the English language classroom. Universities, while framing the syllabus for language teaching, should consider technology as an important tool in the teaching and learning

process. Technical guidance and support should also be given to the teachers in the language classroom to implement technological advances in their teaching process in a successful manner.

References:

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